

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND STRUCTURE OF WOOL FIBER

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Wool has a very complex chemical and physical structure, which corresponds to high natural fiber properties. Wool is one of the most amazing materials and a design masterpiece that can never be replicated in a factory. Wool is a complex, natural and biodegradable protein fiber that can be regenerated and recycled. It has established environmental benefits and this is a natural fiber grown without the use of any herbicides or fertilizers.

The composition of raw wool varies greatly due to many complex factors. An important component is keratin. Wool differs from other natural fibers due to its high sulfur content. The composition of raw wool is as follows: keratin - 45-75%; fat - 5 - 15%; humidity - 10-12%; milk - 2 - 12%; sand and dust - 4-30% and vegetables - 0-5%[1]. Wool fibers grow in small bundles called "sheaths" containing thousands of fibers. Wool fiber is so flexible and elastic that it can be twisted and bent more than 30,000 times without risk of breakage or damage.. Each wool fiber has a natural elasticity that allows it to be stretched by a third and then spring back into place. As a biological product, wool mainly consists of 45.2% carbon, 27.9% oxygen, 6.6% hydrogen, 15.1% nitrogen and 5.2% sulfur. Wool is estimated to contain more than 170 different proteins. These are not evenly distributed along the fiber; proteins of different structures are located in certain regions. This heterogeneous composition is responsible for the different physical and chemical properties of different regions of wool. α - Keratins, which are fibrous proteins, make up 91% of wool. Amino acids are the building blocks of α -keratins. Keratin in wool is called "hard" keratin. This type of keratin is insoluble in water and is very resistant[2]. Keratin is an essential, insoluble protein that consists of eighteen amino acids. The amino acids in wool are cysteine, aspartic acid, serine, alanine, glutamic acid, proline, threonine, isoleucine, glycine, tyrosine, leucine, phenylalanine, valine, histidine, arginine and methionine.. Among these amino acids, cystine has the largest amount, which gives the hair a lot of strength. The molecular structure of wool fibers is like a spiral, which gives wool flexibility and elasticity. The hydrogen bonds connecting the adjacent coils of the helix have a strong effect. There are several micro air pockets in the wool that hold the air. Air pockets have excellent separation properties, making wool fibers ideal for heat protection. The α -helix

of wool is held together by weak hydrogen bonds between amino acids above and below other amino acids in the helix. In wool, individual polypeptide chains join together to form proteins through various covalent (chemical bonds) and non-covalent physical interactions called cross-linking. The most important crosslinks are sulfur-containing disulfide bonds, which are formed during fiber growth through a process called "keratinization.". These bonds make keratin fibers insoluble in water and more resistant to chemical and physical effects than other types of proteins. Disulfide bonds are involved in chemical reactions that occur in the "coating" of fabrics during the finishing process. In this process, the disulphide bonds are rearranged to give wool fabrics smooth drying properties, so that ironing is not required after washing. Another type of cross-linking is an isopeptide bond formed between amino acids containing acidic or basic groups. In addition to chemical crosslinks, some other types of interactions also help to stabilize the fiber under wet and dry conditions. They arise from interactions between side groups of amino acids that make up wool proteins. Thus, hydrophobic interactions occur between hydrocarbon side groups; and ionic interactions occur between groups that can exchange protons[3]. These ionic interactions, or "salt bonds" between acidic (carboxyl) and basic (amino) side chains, are the most important of the non-covalent interactions.. The most important of the non-covalent interactions is the ionic or "salt bond" between the acidic (carboxyl) and basic (amino) side groups. The amphoteric behavior of the carboxyl and amino acids in wool is also important because they give wool its amphoteric or pH buffering properties. This is its ability to absorb and desorb acids and alkalis. Ionic groups also control the dyeing of the fiber by interacting with negatively charged dye molecules.[3].

Literature:

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